

THE DEVELOPMENT OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Levcovich Lavan Limorⁱ

PhD Student,

Institute of International Relations of Moldova (IRIM),

Moldova

Abstract:

In a world of competition between institutions and business companies, we are witnessing the entry of the trend into the world of education, and the most difficult to education for higher education - academia. The academic institutions are undergoing budgetary cuts, thus requiring them to become more efficient and to find additional sources of financial income. Therefore, we will need them to develop marketing and selling capabilities of their educational services. This article will attempt to review the trend, and explain how they came to this period.

Keywords: higher education, globalization, marketing

1. Introduction

The current stage of education services development and changes in educational paradigm are mostly predestined by a variety of factors, most important of which include: processes of globalization and integration into the international educational space; development of information society and economy based on knowledge. New benchmark of XXI century is the development of society and individual based on knowledge and intellectual capacities. Entrepreneurial spirit, systemic thinking, originality and speed of decision-making, creativity, ensure the survival, competitiveness and become the most valuable intangible assets, High speed of life and constant change, introduction of new technologies, increased competition, growth of revenues from the use of intellectual property, Internet penetration in all economic sectors, global informatization and knowledge exchange all these factors marked the beginning of a new stage in economic development and birth of "knowledge" economy [Hemsley-Brown, 2008].

ⁱ Correspondence: email limorllavan@gmail.com

2. Materials

Education is a pure service sector, which is characterized by intangibility, inseparability, heterogeneity and perishability. In addition to that, ownership or the lack of it characterizes this type of service [Gibbs]. Education as a service, then, can be said to be fulfilling the need for learning, acquiring knowledge-providing an intangible benefit (increment in knowledge, professional expertise, skills) produced with the help of a set of tangibles (infrastructure) and intangible components (faculty expertise and learning), where the buyer of the service does not get any ownership. He may have tangible physical evidence to show for the service exchange transaction but the actual benefit accrued is purely intangible in nature [Hemsley].

According to Bledsoe [Bledsoe], in the context of education, the customer only buys access to education, or derives the learning benefit from the services provided. There is no transfer of the ownership of tangibles and intangibles, which have gone into creation of the service product. Payment of fees (price for the service) is just the consideration for access to knowledge and for the use of facilities for a given tenure. Most educational institutions are product oriented rather than market or student oriented. They perceive themselves as producers of certain educational programs, rather than as satisfiers of certain learning needs. This lack of marketing orientation, keeps those managing educational institutions from realizing and exploiting the role that promotion could play in attaining their organizational objectives [Bosman]. Orientation to the world standards of education, improving the quality, relevance and practical applicability of educational products and services become an obligatory part of educational institutes' competitiveness. Learning, curriculums and standards are being renewed according to current advanced technologies as well as requirements of labor market to the level of competence among future specialists. In process of strategical development, education services start to consider versatile customer needs, capabilities and motivation of academics.

Bryman [Bryman] leads an opinion which all this, helps to introduce more marketing tools to the work of institutes. Educational service providers, more than anything, need to be competitive. Often it is the key component of success. The customer simply shows up at the service scape expected to be "serviced". The delivery system in place will satisfy, dissatisfy, or please the customer. And it is always important to remember that the customer cannot be completely separated from the service. Here, the service providers mean teaching fraternity and non-teaching community directly and indirectly associated with the services rendered to the students. Satisfaction and retention of the students solely depends on the way the teachers are in a position to deliver their best services to them [Del Favero]. Haslam [Haslam] indicates that teachers are not treated as "guru", rather they are known as facilitators / services providers. Growth and existence of an educational institute, particularly the professional educational organization depends on the competency, effectiveness, efficiency, sincerity, dedication and devotion of the teaching community

of the institute. People proved as the most vibrant component of educational services marketing mix.

In the present era, it is not natural resources or natural wealth, which distinguish an affluent society from a backward one; it is the accumulation and development of the knowledge resource. Education was never as important a utility as it is today. People however differ in the benefits they seek from the educational services offered to them. It is important, then, in order to be able to satisfy these needs and wants effectively, that a marketing orientation be applied to the conceptualization, design and delivery of educational service [Humphreys & Einsein]. Education planners, in order to plan the service, offer well and deliver it effectively, need to understand the behavior of the target population, and the criteria they use to exercise choice. Another key issue to better delivery of the education service is that it is performed for people and by people. People therefore represent the starting point for analysis to precede conceptualizing the service offer and developing it into a marketable service package. The education service offered by the institution must reflect the organizational response to the identified needs and wants of the target segment, in a given socio-economic context. However, the beginning of successful service delivery in this case is in satisfying the needs of service providers [Jackson, Nunn]. If university focuses its marketing activities on the needs of practical implementation of gained knowledge, it is particularly important to develop requirements for the quality of educational services and technology to maintain the quality management system. Quality of education is necessary condition of university's competitiveness in context of international integration and high domestic competition. It most importantly depends on the quality of human resources and so one of the main directions of higher education development should be the development of teacher's potential.

In this regard, development the strategy of university professors' potential involvement plays an invaluable role in internal relationship marketing. Each school must have a current program of training and supporting its personnel, which, in turn, is part of the strategic marketing plan for the development of the institution. At this moment, building an effective system of respectable earnings for higher education employees is task of socio-economic nature. Reputational strength and position of university's employees in education market depends on how well this system built. Nunn [Nunn] which made a research on service providers for satisfaction, analyze the effectiveness of salaries and incentives for employees of higher education system. His research was conducted on the basis of motivational factors. In his conclusions, he found that the system of payment and incentives for university workers requires significant adjustment by university's social policies strengthening. The results indicate on some points:

- The current payment system does not consider teacher rating made by students (the main consumer of educational services). Many universities hold contests for the title of "Best Lecturer", but this is not stimulated in any significant material way.
- Motivation for instructional and guiding work virtually does not exist.

- Most faculty members do not understand new wage system; therefore, the attitude toward it is ambiguous.
- The majority of teachers moonlight in other universities in part-time status, considering the possibility to look for jobs as an extra incentive to teaching.

According to Packard [Packard], the relationship marketing concept human resources are crucial for market success. The value of human resources in marketing mix of the university is not limited by availability of highly qualified, professional teachers, transferring knowledge in classrooms. From marketing perspective university staff has a huge impact on the consumer, i.e. the student both directly in the learning process and in extracurricular time it is a style of communication with students and other clients of the university, the speed of response to inquiries, complaints, etc. Teachers and staff should establish an educational environment that best meets the needs of a quality education.

Human factor is critical strategic resource of university effectiveness in education market. In this case, teaching resources appear as human resource and component of strategic resources that contribute to an increase in marketing opportunities of the university [Rosser et al.]. Human resources formation in terms of marketing is subject to the problem of achieving university competitiveness and further sustainable integrated development of human resources on labor market. Further development of university staff is based on principles of material resources rational use; modernization of the educational process based on innovative educational technologies according to customer requirements for quality education. The basic problems of university human resources in modern world is the need to find new forms and methods in accordance to new educational paradigm that requires a change in teaching and teacher's role. Franck & Optiz [Franck & Optiz] describes the development of the educational establishment in the global age by a new Comparative characteristic of teacher's role in the framework of classical and new educational paradigm. They do not try to prove that the method is flawed, but rather to ensure that the work processes are unique and that the consumer - the client - the student will feel the competitive advantage of the educational institution over the other institutions. The attractiveness of the educational institution will result in its financial success. The success will be reflected in an increase in the demand of students to study in the academic institution, and in their satisfaction with the work processes and the educational service they receive. The following table attempts to show the changes made in these institutions:

Table 1: presentation of comparative characteristics of teacher's role
in the framework of classical and new educational paradigm

Classical Educational Paradigm	New Educational Paradigm
Main mission of education: to prepare new generation for life and work	Main mission of education: to ensure the conditions for personal self-determination and self-realization
Human being is a simple system	Human being is complicated system
Knowledge comes from the past ("school of memory")	Knowledge comes from the future ("school of thought")

Education – transferring to student known samples of knowledge and skills	Education – creation the image of world itself through active lodging in the world of objective, social, and spiritual culture
Student – object of pedagogical impact, someone who is being taught	Student – subject of cognitive activity, someone who perceives knowledge
From subject to object, monological relationship between teacher and student	From subject to object, dialogue between teacher and student
“ Responsive ”, reproductive student activity	“ Active ”, creative student learning activities

Source: [Barr & Tagg]

According to the data from the table, as the society move to a knowledge society, education technologies are becoming more customer-oriented, and the recipients of knowledge become more responsible for their own learning. It should be noted that the process of teaching and methods of knowledge transfer over 50 years virtually unchanged. However, modern conditions require educational systems to be more flexible, able to quickly adapt to change. Also, position of teacher fundamentally changed [Trash, 2009]. Now university professor must not only transmit knowledge to learners, but to be their consultant to the world's knowledge, help them to understand the importance of learning and personal responsibility for the results of their studies. Examination of educational trends, terms of university development, marketing principles and problems of university human resources transformation led to the conclusion that modern university is in dire need for highly qualified teaching staff, that is able to adapt quickly to new educational standards, accept changes, create high quality educational products. Time of spontaneous management has passed. Now it is necessary to build a systematic approach to solving of teaching resources complex development problem according to the criteria of modern education system and differential requirements for the quality of education for all segments of consumers [Wang et al.].

3. Leadership in Educational System

Leadership has been recognized as a vital focus in the field of organizational behavior in which it is one of the dynamic effects during individual and organizational interactions. Leadership undoubtedly has the major role in the outcome of any project in which all identified leadership styles have variable outcomes under different situations [Woods].

Today’s, academic leaders must have varieties of leadership skills to be effective in an organization. Many literatures done by researchers showed that there are many components of effective leadership that can take place in educational sector including the ability be to a role model for the followers, capability to lead a number of faculty varieties, and to have a critical thinking skill. It is important for the academic dean, deputy of dean and head of department as a leader, to adapt to the appropriate

leadership style that suits him or her with the groups for which he or she is responsible for [Nunn, 2008]. Academic leaders are responsible as the chief academic officers of their divisions or faculties. Nevertheless, the university's hierarchy acts as the middle manager to play the role as the mediators between the executive level administrations, the chairpersons, and the faculty of the respective universities. The main responsibility of the academic leaders is they must operate within the university system in which it has numbers of characteristics to deal with and therefore, academic leaders must navigate the bureaucracies of the university in order to successfully lead their divisions. However, the leadership style of academic leaders is varied and diverse due to the no formal professional training provided who seek for this position (McGregor, 2005) as well as no consistency in the job descriptions for academic leaders which lead to further uncertainty about their roles and accountabilities. Hence & Gmelch [Hence & Gmelch, 2004] agreed that academic leaders need to be taught leadership skills in order to decrease the unprofessional nature of the leadership in the ranks of administrations. Further argued by Packard [Packard, 2008], indicated that one of the significant challenges faced by the many leaders today is in terms of their ability to adapt to a constant global environment changing and at the same time to maintain the internal self-motivated of the organizations. Therefore, the appropriate selection of leadership style adapted by academic leaders is important in order to play a major role in the succession of the overall organizational performance of their academic units.

In the literature, leadership has been recognized as a vital focus in the field of organizational behavior in which it is one of the dynamics effects during individual and organizational interactions. Leadership undoubtedly has a major role in the outcome of any project in which all identified leadership styles have variable outcomes under different situations. Fry [Fry, 2003] explains that leadership plays a strategic tool to motivate the staff to enhance their potential growth and development. On the other hand, organizational performance refers to ability of an organization to achieve certain objectives and goals such as good financial results, high organization profit, and produce high quality products by using effective strategies adopted. Under certain circumstances, transactional style of leadership lead to a successful work of the organizations even though it does not give the followers as much right as transformational leadership does but it does give the followers a sense of identity and job satisfaction. On the contrary, other stud is suggested that transformational leadership had a greater role to play regarding followers' performance and creativity compared to the transactional leadership. Furthermore, the discussion on the relationship between leadership styles and performance has been discussed often by the scholars. Many researches done before showed the results that leadership styles have significant relation with the organizational performance, in which different style of leadership can determine the relationship between the leadership styles and the organizational performance either it may have positive correlation or negative correlation. Transformational theory suggests that effective leaders can generate and encourage an appropriate idea or image of the organizations. They are more goals and vision-oriented leaders who seek to achieve their desired intentions to be fulfilled.

According to Bryman [Bryman, 2007], the transformational leadership in the educational setting is more likely to sustain the educational system change. In relation to the leadership styles within the higher education settings, many academic leaders prefer transformational leadership. The transformational leaders motivate their followers to be fully aware the importance of their tasks outcomes and induce them to exceed their own self-interest for the sake of the organizations by achieving their higher needs. One of the main elements of this type of leadership is transformational at its core which elevates both leaders and the followers. Avolio [Avolio] supports the theory that transformational leadership is morally inspiring, a quality that differentiates it from other leadership styles. As the overall of this theory dictates that the leaders must have the capability to response to the demands in any circumstances. Particularly, leaders who operate under this leadership must be aware of their environment surrounding, abilities of their employees, and to be flexible in their leadership approach [Bledsoe, 2008].

References

1. Avolio, B.J. (2007). Promoting More Integrative Strategies for Leadership Theory-Building. *American Psychologist*, 62(1), p. 25-33.
2. Bledsoe, R.W. (2008). *An Award-Winning School: The Impact of Transformational Leadership on Teacher Morale in the Middle School*. Doctoral dissertation, Capella University, Minneapolis, MN, p. 332-338.
3. Boseman, G., (2008). Effective leadership in a changing world. *Journal of Financial Service Professionals*, 62(3), p. 36-38.
4. Bryman, A. (2007). Effective leadership in higher education: A literature review. *Studies in Higher Education*, 32(6), p. 693-710.
5. Franck, E., & Opitz, C. (2005). Incentive structures for professors in Germany and the US: Implications for cross-national borrowing in higher education reform. *Comparative Education Review*, p.51-71.
6. Fry, L.W. (2003). Towards a Theory of Spiritual Leadership. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 14, p. 193-227.
7. Gmelch, W. H. (2004). The Department Chair's Balancing Acts. *New Directions for Higher Education*, 126, p. 69-84
8. Haslam, J. (2002). Learning the lesson - speaking up for communication as an academic discipline too important to be sidelined. *Journal of Communication Management*, 7(1), p. 14-20.
9. Humphreys, J.H., & Einstein, W. O. (2004). Leadership and temperament congruence: Extending the expectancy model of work motivation. *Journal of Leadership and Organizational Studies*, 10(4), 58-79.
10. J. Hemsley-Brown (2008) Universities in a competitive global marketplace *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 19 (4) p. 316 – 322.

11. McGregor, S. (2005). Determining Professional Development Needs of Aspiring and Current Division Chairs/Deans of the Louisiana Community
12. Nunn, G.M. (2008). The perceived leadership skills needed to improve the effectiveness of charge nurses: A "ground dad theory study" USA. p. 211 – 225.
13. P. Gibbs, F. Marketing Higher Education: Theory and Practice Open University Press (2008), p. 113
14. Packard, J.A. (2008). Analyzing the Intersection of Leadership Practices, Emotional Intelligence, and Coping Responses in Women-Owned. London University, UK. P. 33 – 54.
15. Rosser, V.J., Johnsrud, L. K., & Heck, R. H. (2003). Academic deans and directors: Assessing their effectiveness from individual and Sciences, (49). 134-142
16. Thrash Alberta (2012). Leadership in Higher Education International. Journal of Humanities and Social Science, 2(13), 1-12.
17. Wang, F.J., Shieh, C.J., & Tang, M.L., (2010). Effect of Leadership Style on Organizational Performance as Viewed from Hum a Resource. Washington, DC. USA. P. 151 – 170.
18. Woods, P.A. (2004) 'Democratic leadership: drawing distinctions with distributed leadership'. International Journal of Leadership in Education, 7(1), 3-26, World Bank Data.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Social Sciences Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).